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Review Article

FANCONI ANAEMIA: A REVIEW

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Abstract

Fanconi anaemia is a rare genetic disorder which leads to bone marrow failure and results in decreased production of all types of blood cells. The frequency of occurrence is greater in South-African Africaners, sub-saharan blacks, and spanish gypsies than in the overall world population. This rare genetic disease occurs when two people with the recessive gene have children. There is no cure available for falconi anaemia, the treatment for falconi anaemia is symptomatic.

Keywords: *fanconi anemia, rare genetic disease, growth factors*

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- Hearing test
- HLA tissue typing(to find matching bone-marrow donors)
- Ultrasound of the kidneys
- Antibiotics (possibly given through a vein) to treat infections
- Blood transfusions to treat symptoms due to low blood counts

TREATMENT:

There is no cure available for falconi anaemia,the treatment for falconi anaemia is **symptomatic**.

Medicines called growth factors (such as erythropoietin, G-CSF, and GM-CSF) can improve blood counts for a short while. A bone marrow transplant can cure the blood count problems of Fanconi anemia. (The best bone marrow donor is a brother or sister whose tissue type matches the person affected by Fanconi anemia). People who have had a successful bone marrow transplant still need regular check-ups because of the risk for additional cancers. Hormone therapy combined with low doses of steroids (such as hydrocortisone or prednisone) is prescribed to those who do not have a bone marrow donor. Most people respond to hormone therapy. But everyone with the disorder will quickly get worse when the drugs are stopped. In most cases, these drugs eventually stop working. Additional treatments may include:

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